

A novel empirical approximation of π involving e , ϕ and $\sqrt{3}$ based on a modified Gregory-Leibniz series

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Abstract: This paper presents a novel empirical approach for approximating $\pi = 3.1415\dots$, using the Euler's number (e), the golden ratio (ϕ) and the irrational number $\sqrt{3}$. Additionally, it discusses and reviews well-known formulas and techniques developed throughout history to approximate π .

Key-words: Euler's number; golden ratio; irrational numbers; π approximation.

1 Introduction

The history of the number π dates back thousands of years and continues to fascinate the humankind in the modern era. Ancient civilizations had various ways of estimating π . The Babylonians used $3\frac{1}{8} = 3.125$; while the Egyptians were more precise assuming $\frac{256}{81} \approx 3.1604$. Archimedes, on the other hand, found a beautiful correlation that remains notable to this days: $3\frac{10}{71} < \pi < 3\frac{1}{7}$ [1].

Computing a large number of digits of π has no practical scientific or engineering applications. This can be easily understood when it is needed only 40 digits of π to compute the circumference of the Milky Way Galaxy to an error less than a size of a proton. However, computing digits of π stimulated research into advanced computational techniques, that lead to efficient computing linear convolutions and fast Fourier transforms (FFTs). Moreover, π calculations are excellent tools for testing the computer integrity, like hardware and software ones [1].

Throughout the history of mathematics, countless formulas involving π had been discovered, and a vast number of books and papers have been written to explore them. [1] formally describes a large number of π formulas and their interrelations. The authors wrote about the history of π and the run time of various algorithms for computing various π digits.

Considering different approaches for analyzing π , [2] presented the BBP formula. This formula was the first to calculate n -th digit of π in hexadecimal. Furthermore, [3] exposed the life of π detailing its historical development and highlighting notable formulas by Ramanujan, the Chudnovskys, and the BBP formula. He also discussed the influence of π on modern computing and popular culture.

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2 Objective of the Paper

The main focus of this paper is not to provide a fast approximation nor an intrinsic and elegant theorem of π , but rather to introduce an interesting empirical correlation between π , e , ϕ , and $\sqrt{3}$. In addition, this paper will not cover the history of π , but will highlight some interesting formulas that were important in the old days and remain relevant in contemporary mathematics.

3 Some Famous Approximations of π Throughout History

Over the centuries, many brilliant mathematicians have proposed formulas to approximate the value of π . These expressions vary in origin, complexity, and accuracy, which reflect the historical context and mathematical tools available at that time. In this section, it is briefly reviewed some of the most well-known approximations and formulas from ancient estimations to elegant modern series.

3.1 Wallis Formula

One of the famous pre-Newtonian formula for π is the Wallis formula [6]. It can be expressed as an infinite product:

$$\frac{\pi}{2} = \frac{2 \cdot 2}{1 \cdot 3} \frac{4 \cdot 4}{3 \cdot 5} \frac{6 \cdot 6}{5 \cdot 7} \cdots \quad (1)$$

This infinite product might be written in product form as:

$$\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{4i^2 - 1}{4i^2} = \frac{\pi}{2}, \quad (2)$$

which led to the discovery of the Gamma function [3]. Besides the mathematical approach for finding the Wallis formula, which can be derived from different ways, [6] obtained the Wallis formula using quantum mechanics, in the author's words: "obtained directly from the variational approach to the spectrum of the hydrogen atom in spaces of arbitrary dimensions greater than one, including the physical three dimensions".

3.2 Brouncker identity

In 1655 William Brouncker converted the Wallis infinite product in an continuous infinite fraction [4], such as:

$$\frac{4}{\pi} = 1 + \frac{1^2}{2 + \frac{3^2}{2 + \frac{5^2}{2 + \frac{7^2}{2 + \dots}}}} \quad (3)$$

3.3 Gregory-Leibniz Series

After the development of calculus by Newton and Leibniz, this branch of mathematics became a tool for finding new formulas for π [3]. A formula that comes from that subject is the following one:

$$\tan^{-1}x = \int_0^x \frac{dt}{1+t^2} = \int_0^x (1-t^2+t^4-t^6+\dots)dt, \quad (4)$$

solving the integral leads to:

$$\tan^{-1}x = x - \frac{x^3}{3} + \frac{x^5}{5} - \frac{x^7}{7} + \frac{x^9}{9} - \dots \quad (5)$$

Substituting $x = 1$ reaches the Gregory-Leibniz formula:

$$\frac{\pi}{4} = 1 - \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{5} - \frac{1}{7} + \frac{1}{9} - \frac{1}{11} + \dots \quad (6)$$

3.4 Ramanujan's Formulas

Srinivasa Ramanujan (1887 - 1920) was the most genius Indian mathematician of all time. In his short career, he wrote and discovered more than 120 theorems and formulas, which some of them lacked rigorous proofs. Considering the number π , Ramanujan developed 14 formulas/series for $\frac{1}{\pi}$, but he never gave much explanations about the origin of the formulas [4].

It is acknowledged that this paper does not present a full historical account of π , in this sense is presented 5 of the most famous Ramanujan's formulas. The first is a beautiful series that remains to this days as one of most particular and elegant π series of all the time.

$$\frac{1}{\pi} = \frac{\sqrt{8}}{9801} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(4n)!^4}{n!} \frac{[1103 + 26390n]}{396^{4n}}. \quad (7)$$

The second notable expansion is:

$$\frac{1}{\pi} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \binom{2n}{n}^3 \frac{42n+5}{2^{12n+4}}. \quad (8)$$

With what was presented, it is possible to notice the creativity of Ramanujan and the great capacity of linking hard expressions with one idea, the number π . Besides these two series, Ramanujan discovered more different relations with numbers and π [3]. Some of them are:

$$\pi \approx \frac{3}{\sqrt{67}} \log(5280), \quad \pi \approx \frac{3}{\sqrt{163}} \log(640320), \quad \pi \approx \left(9^2 + \frac{19^2}{22}\right)^{1/4}. \quad (9)$$

3.5 Chudnovsky Algorithm

The Chudnovsky algorithm is one of the most fast methods for calculating π digits and is based on the theory of modular forms and the Ramanujan-type series. This algorithm generates 14 or more digits of π for every summation step. Due to the fact, of its capacity, the algorithm it has been used to achieve numerous world record calculations for π [7]. In this way, the algorithm based on [5] is:

$$\frac{1}{\pi} = 12 \sum_0^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k (6k)! (545140134k + 13591409)}{(3k)! (k!)^3 (640320)^{3k + \frac{3}{2}}}. \quad (10)$$

3.6 BBP Algorithm

[2] formally presented a new type of algorithm for π digits. This algorithm can compute n -th digit of π without generating the previous ones in the hexadecimal base. Based on that, the formula is:

$$\pi = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{16^i} \left(\frac{4}{8i+1} - \frac{2}{8i+4} - \frac{1}{8i+5} - \frac{1}{8i+6} \right). \quad (11)$$

4 The new formulation

The novel insight presented in this paper can be visualized in this section. It is well-known that the Gregory-Leibniz formula can be written in a series form as:

$$\frac{\pi}{4} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^i}{2i+1}. \quad (12)$$

Due to some empirical manipulation in the Gregory-Leibniz series, it is possible to find the following series, that matches π , e , ϕ and $\sqrt{3}$.

$$\pi = 4 e^x \phi \sqrt{3} \sum_{i=2}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^i}{2i+1} \quad (13)$$

where, $0.858787 < x < 0.86$, and $\phi = \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}$.

The beauty of this formula is the fact that it can concatenate the Euler's number, the golden ratio and $\sqrt{3}$ to approximate π . These constants were chosen due to the fact that the intention was to combine different constants to approximate one. This works numerically because it derives from the first two steps of the Gregory-Leibniz formula.

5 Numerical Results

To approximate π it was used a computer with 16 GB RAM and AMD Ryzen 7 4800H with Radeon Graphics 2.90 GHz. The code was written in Python.

One of the difficulties with this empirical approximation is related to the uncertainty of the x value. If it is used a number x with 9 decimals, the series converges to π with a 9-digit precision. In this sense, using $x = 0.858787165$ the author achieved an approximation for the first 9 digits of π . The following expression shows that:

$$3.141592653377146\dots = 4 e^{0.858787165} \phi \sqrt{3} \sum_{i=2}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^i}{2i+1}. \quad (14)$$

The Figure 1 shows the comparison between the Gregory-Leibniz series and the Empirical formula presented in this study. The graphic put on view the convergence to an absolute error ($\pi - \pi_{approx}$) of each formula considering a 1000 terms. To understand the precision of each of them Table 1 presents the absolute final values of each one. It is possible to conclude that both of the formulas reach more than 99% of similarity with π , showing a great capacity of convergence. Moreover, its possible to highlight the precision of the Empirical formula using famous constants to approximate π , that reveals the beauty of mathematics and its correlations.

Figure 1: The convergence in log scale.

Table 1: Absolute error of each series after 1000 terms.

Formula	Absolute Error (%)
Gregory-Leibniz Series	0.099%
Empirical Formula	0.668%

6 Conclusion

In light of what was presented, it is possible to perceive that the history of number π is vast through the human history, fascinating persons from the first centuries until the modern days. A wide variety of formulas, series and algorithms were developed in the past 2000 years to approximate π . Some of them focused on the beauty of the formula, others focused on the computational efficiency of it. In this paper, it was shown a new formulation, that does not result in a fast algorithm or formula, nor implicate in a great approximation for π , but it illustrates an interesting correlation between different irrational numbers and how they can be correlated in some sense.

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